

STAR

STRUCTURAL
ARCHITECTURE

CONCURSO DE ESTUDIANTES PARA UNA
ARQUITECTURA TRANSFORMABLE
STUDENT COMPETITION ON
TRANSFORMABLE ARCHITECTURE

EDITOR: F. ESCRIG

14

Abstract:**CRumpled Umbrella**

A crumpling gesture is turned into a canopy skeleton. The Process starts with the study of the crumpled paper. By studying the hand effects of the crumpling of a paper, we get an analysis of it into mountains and valleys.

There are three points that lead the paper's movement. These points become the vectors of the structure's forces. Consequently, they consist of the columns of the structure.

A metal skeleton is produced, which can receive on the top several materials, such as fabric or glass. According to the top material, we get sun and rain protection.

How to cite:

Christou, M., Vyzoviti, S., & De Souza Sánchez, P. M. (2013). CRumbled Umbrella. *Star Structural Architecture. Student competition on transformable architecture*. Editorial Starbooks. 76-77. ISSN 1137-201X DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8348370>

EDITORIAL STARBOOKS

Calle Guadalupe, 12. 41003. Sevilla
Tel.: 954-4556583
Fax: 954-4556606
e-mail: editorialstarbooks@gmail.com
www.starbooks.es

CONCURSO DE ESTUDIANTES TRANSFORMABLES 2013.
PRIMERA EDICIÓN. 2013.

Director: Félix Escrig Pallarés
Maquetación: José Sánchez Sánchez
Imprime: Argüelles S. A.
ISSN: 1137-201 X
Depósito Legal: SE 2256-96

Portada:
Imágenes del primer Premio del Concurso de Estudiantes TRANSFORMABLES2013

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STRUCTURAL ARCHITECTURE 14

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TRANSFORMABLE ARCHITECTURE

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ARQUITECTURA TRANSFORMABLE

Eds: Felix Escrig & José Sánchez

ÍNDICE

JURADO Y FALLO DEL CONCURSO	3
RELACIÓN DE PARTICIPANTES	4
PROPUESTAS	6

CR UMPLED UMBRELLA

- _ A CRUMPLING GESTURE IS TURNED INTO A CANOPY SKELETON
- _ THE PROCESS STARTS WITH THE STUDY OF THE CRUMPLED PAPER
- _ BY STUDYING HOW THE HAND AFFECTS THE CRUMPLING OF A PAPER, WE GET AN ANALYSIS OF IT INTO MOUNTAINS AND THE VALLEYS
- _ THERE ARE THREE POINTS WHICH LEAD THE PAPER'S MOVEMENT
- _ THESE POINTS BECOME THE VECTORS OF THE STRUCTURE'S FORCES
- _ CONSEQUENTLY THEY CONSIST THE COLUMNS OF THE STRUCTURE
- _ A METAL SKELETON IS PRODUCED, WHICH CAN RECEIVE ON THE TOP SEVERAL MATERIALS, SUCH AS FABRIC OR GLASS
- _ ACCORDING TO TOP MATERIAL, WE GET SUN AND RAIN PROTECTION

_FROM THE PAPER MODEL TO THE STRAWS AND ROPES
 _THE PURPOSE IS TO CREATE FLEXIBLE JOINTS AND RIGID EDGES
 _MATERIALS USED: Ø8 ALUMINUM TUBES
 ELASTIC ROPE
 3MM STAINLESS STEEL WIRE ROPE CLIP
 _IN THE BASE THE ELASTIC ROPES FROM THE 3 COLUMNS ARE
 CONNECTED WITH A COMPACTED METAL RING
 _THE FOUNDATION INCLUDES A BARREL FULL OF SAND, IN ORDER TO
 ENABLE THE REGULAR MOVEMENT OF THE COLUMNS

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PEDIDOS A STARBOOKS:

Tel: (95) 455.65.83 Fax: (95) 455.66.06

editorialstarbooks@gmail.com

<http://www.starbooks.es>

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